

Synergistic effect of ZnO/carbon nano composite for the photocatalytic degradation of the dye acid yellow 110

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Abstract : The zinc oxide/carbon (ZnO/C) nano composite was prepared by self-propagating solution combustion method by using dextrose as a fuel and carbon source. The prepared catalyst was characterized by XRD, SEM, EDAX and BET analysis techniques. The nanoZnO/C composite exhibited enhanced photocatalytic activity for the degradation of acid yellow 110 when compared with commercial ZnO and pristine nanoZnO. The photocatalytic activities of composites with different amounts of carbon were evaluated for the degradation of the dye. The best photocatalytic activity was observed for a sample with a 10% of carbon. The influence of various parameters such as the initial dye concentration, pH and catalyst weight on the photocatalytic degradation of the dye was studied. The optimum pH was found to be 6.2. The dye degradation obeyed first order kinetics and could be explained on the basis of Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism. The electrical energy efficiency for the degradation of dye was also determined. The efficiency of the ZnO/C nano composite catalyst was also tested for the degradation of real time effluent collected from textile industry. The reduction in the COD values of the treated effluent indicated a complete destruction of the organic molecules along with the color removal.

Keywords : NanoZnO/C composite, acid yellow 110, degradation, photo catalysis, effluent.

Introduction

Water pollution is ubiquitous and poses a serious threat to the environment. The major source of pollutants are arising from the industries such as textile, paper, cosmetics and leather industries in which organic dyes are widely used. Most of these dyes are carcinogenic and are not amenable for biological degradation. Among the various methods used, semiconductor mediated photo catalysis has been found to be an effective and cheap method for removing these organic pollutants from wastewaters. The various semiconductors such as TiO₂, ZnO, Fe₂O₃, CdS and ZnS are being used as photo catalysts¹⁻⁵. Further, the use of nanoparticles of these catalysts exhibit higher photocatalytic activity than their bulk counterparts by increasing surface area and porosity⁶⁻¹⁰. TiO₂ is considered to be the best photo catalyst and has been widely used for the degradation of colored organics¹¹. However, widespread use of TiO₂ is not economical for large scale water treatment operations. Ample information has been documented in literature, with regard to higher photo catalytic efficiency of ZnO over TiO₂. This has attracted the attention

of many researchers to further explore the potential of ZnO in various photocatalytic reactions¹²⁻¹⁵. The main drawback of ZnO is its photo instability and photo corrosion on UV irradiation. Nowadays, many methods are in practice to improve its photo stability. This includes surface organic coating of ZnO¹⁶ and surface hybridization of ZnO with carbon and fullerenes C₆₀^{17,18}. In this connection various experiments have been conducted to enhance the rate of photo degradation of ZnO by coupling with adsorbent like activated carbon which provides high concentration of target substances around the catalyst particulate^{19,20}.

The main focus of this study is to synthesize and characterize the ZnO/C nano composite and compare its photocatalytic activity with commercial ZnO and pristine nanoZnO in the degradation of the dye acid yellow 110 in water under UV irradiation in the batch reactor and also to study the effect of carbon loading on nanoZnO in the degradation of the dye. The influence of various experimental parameters such as catalyst weight, initial dye concentration and effect of pH has been studied. A detailed

Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic model has been proposed and kinetic parameters are evaluated from the experimental data. The electrical energy efficiency for the degradation of dye is examined. The photo degradation studies are also carried out for the treatment of textile effluent collected from dyeing unit situated near Tirupur town, Tamilnadu, India.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the catalyst :

The synthesized ZnO/C photocatalyst with 10% of carbon was characterized using advanced instrumentation techniques. The scanning electron microscopy of the sample was performed to determine the morphology and size of the particles. The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained using an X-ray diffractometer equipped with a monochromatic high-intensity CuK α radiation. Fig. 2 shows the XRD pattern of ZnO/C nano composite. The sharp peak indicates the crystalline nature of the ZnO/C carbon [JCPDS card no. 36-1451]. The XRD patterns were iden-

tical to the hexagonal phase with wurtzite structure with space group [C6V = P6₃ mc] and unit cell parameters $a = b = 3.248 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.1 \text{ \AA}$. The crystallite size was calculated from the following Debye-Scherer formula.

$$d = \frac{K\lambda}{B \cos \theta_B}$$

where K is 0.89 (Scherer's constant), λ is the wavelength of X-rays, θ_B is the Bragg diffraction angle and B is the full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the highly intense diffraction peak. Using the Debye-Scherer formula, the average crystallite size of ZnO/C was found to be 22 nm respectively. The XRD pattern of the composite revealed the hexagonal phase with wurtzite structure and also the nano crystalline nature of the catalyst. The particle size and morphology of nano particles analysed by SEM are shown in Fig. 3. This image reveals that the entire product is comprised of spherical nano particles with the average size of 22.18 nm which is in good agree-

Fig. 1. Structure of acid yellow 110.

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of ZnO/carbon nano composite.

Fig. 3. SEM image of ZnO/carbon nano composite.

ment with calculations based on Scherer formula of the XRD pattern. Fig. 4 indicates the EDAX pattern of ZnO/C nano composite in which the presence of carbon, zinc and oxygen were indicated. The percentage of carbon loaded on to the catalyst samples were determined by EDAX analysis (Table 1) and further it was confirmed by gravimetric analysis of the samples. The EDAX mapping of ZnO/C nano composite shown in Fig. 5 indicates the

Fig. 4. EDAX elemental analysis of ZnO/carbon nano composite.

Table 1. EDAX analysis of ZnO/C nano composites

Sample	Elements (weight %)		
	OK	ZnK	CK
ZnO/C	29.71	52.31	17.98

Electron Image

Fig. 5. EDAX mapping of ZnO/carbon nano composite.

presence of oxygen, zinc and carbon respectively. The specific surface area is an important micro structural parameter of ZnO/C nano composite which depends on the geometrical shape and porosity of the particles and it was found to be 110 m²/g (Fig. 6) and the data was given in Table 2.

UV-Vis spectrophotometer was employed to record the absorbance spectra in the wavelength range of 200 to

Fig. 6. BET isotherm of ZnO/carbon nano composite.

Table 2. Surface characteristics of the catalyst. BET-specific surface area ($S_{BET} \pm 2$ m²/g), BJH-cumulative surface area ($S_C \pm 2$ m²/g), BJH-average cumulative pore volume ($V_p^C \pm 0.002$ cm³/g) and pore diameter (d_p in Å)

Catalyst	S_{BET}	V_p^C	d_p
ZnO/C	110	0.155378	56.159

1000 nm for dispersed ZnO/C nano composite in distilled water. The absorbance spectrum of ZnO/C nano composite is shown in Fig. 7. A strong absorption band ranging from 200 to 500 nm was observed for ZnO/C nano composite due to the zinc ion. ZnO/carbon nano composite shows a strong absorbance at 430 nm, similar absorptions have been previously reported and have been attributed to oxygen vacancies, because carbon moved some oxygen on the ZnO phase²².

Fig. 7. UV-Visible spectrum of the ZnO/carbon nano composite.

Kinetics and photodegradation studies of acid yellow 110 :

The photo degradability of the dye was investigated by exposing the dye solution to UV light in the presence of photocatalysts such as commercial ZnO, pristine nanoZnO and nanoZnO/C composite separately. It was observed that the nanoZnO/C composite decolorizes the dye faster than commercial ZnO and pristine nanoZnO. It was also observed that about 70% of the dye degraded within 10 min in the presence of nanoZnO/C composite, whereas in the presence of commercial ZnO and nanoZnO the degradation of the dye was found to be 47% and 55% respectively as shown in Fig. 8. The higher degradation of nanoZnO/C composite may be attributed to the higher surface area ($110 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) of the catalyst and an enhanced

Fig. 8. Photodegradability of acid yellow 110 : [Acid yellow] = $60 \mu\text{M}$, Catalyst = 0.5 g/L ; pH = 6.2; Temp. = $30.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; incident wavelength = 254 nm ; absorbance measured at 420 nm . (1) Dye treated with commercial ZnO, (2) Dye treated with pristine nanoZnO and (3) Dye treated with ZnO/carbon nano composite.

adsorption due to carbon which is a prerequisite for photodegradation²³. The preliminary results suggest that nanoZnO/C composite can be used as effective photocatalyst for the degradation of dye acid yellow 110. To study the effect of carbon loading on nanoZnO, the degradation studies on acid yellow 110 was carried using three different samples of ZnO/C composite consisting of 5%, 10% and 20% of carbon. The results indicated that the catalyst consisting of 10% carbon was found to be effective in the degradation of the dye. The optimum carbon loading was found to be 10%. The loading of carbon greater than or

less than 10% was found to decrease the degradation rate of the dye²⁴. This may be due to masking effect of excess carbon which prevents the ZnO particle separation during the degradation studies at higher carbon loading. Whereas the decrease in the degradation rate of the dye in the case of carbon loading less than 10% may be attributed to premature combustion due to insufficient fuel which leading to decrease in the surface area of nanoZnO/C composite ($17 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$). The Fig. 9 shows the UV-Vis absorption spectra of acid yellow 110 by exposure to UV light for 30, 60 and 90 min in the presence of ZnO/C nano composite with 10% of carbon. It was seen after irradiating for 30 min, the absorption peak intensity sharply decreased. After that, it decreased gradually with increasing exposure time. It demonstrated that the synthesized ZnO/C nano composite has good photocatalytic degradation efficiency in UV light. The complete mineralization of dye was observed in the presence of nanoZnO/C nano composite (Table 3). Based on this fact, further studies were carried out using nanoZnO/C catalyst containing surface area $110 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$.

Fig. 9. Absorption spectrum of acid yellow 110 in the presence of ZnO/carbon nano composite at different time intervals. [Acid yellow] = $60 \mu\text{M}$; pH = 6.2; Catalyst = 0.5 g/L ; Temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; incident wavelength = 254 nm ; absorbance measured at 420 nm .

Table 3. Analytical data for the mineralization of acid yellow 110

Element	Theoretical (%)	Experimental (%)	Percentage of mineralization
C	36.71	35.60	97
N	10.71	10.38	97
S	12.23	11.86	97

The effect of pH on the degradation of the dye was studied from 5.0 to 8.0. The photo degradation efficiency of the dye increased from pH 5.0 to 6.2. Further increase in pH above 6.2 decreases the degradation efficiency. This can be explained on the basis of acid base property of the metal oxide by taking into consideration zero point charge of ZnO (8.0)²⁵. The catalyst surface was positively charged in acidic medium and negatively charged in basic medium. The higher efficiency in acid medium is due to the electrostatic interactions between the positive catalyst surface and dye anions leading to strong adsorption of the latter on the metal oxide support. This accounts for the effective decolourization of the dye at pH 6.2. Moreover at this pH there is also formation of OH[•] radicals which also react with the dye molecules and enhance the decolourization process²⁶.

Fig. 10. Plot of $\log C_0/C$ versus time for acid yellow 110. Catalyst = ZnO/C (0.5 g/L); pH = 6.2; Temp. = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 420 nm.

The effect of catalyst loading on the photo degradation of AY 110 was carried out by varying the amount of ZnO/C catalyst from 0.25 to 1.00 g/L. The photo degradation rate was found to increase with an increase of catalyst loading from 0.25 to 0.5 g/L. Further increase in catalyst loading resulted in decrease in the degradation rate. This can be explained in terms of availability of active sites on the catalyst surface and penetration of UV light into the suspension. The total active surface area increases with increasing catalyst weight but at the catalyst weight above optimum loading there is a decrease in UV light penetration due to screening effect of excess catalyst particles in the solution. Hence, the initial rate decreases at the higher catalyst loading. The optimum

catalyst loading was found to be 0.5 g/L. Similar results were reported in the decolorisation of acid red 14 on ZnO²⁷.

The effect of initial concentration of dye was studied in the range of 20–100 μM. The initial rate of photo degradation of the dye increased from 1.7 to 4.2 μM/min with an increase in concentration from 20–60 μM and further increase in concentration resulted in decrease in the rate. At higher concentration, a larger number of dye molecules were adsorbed, virtually masking the surface of the catalyst particle and preventing the photons from interacting with the catalyst²⁸.

Kinetic investigation :

Photocatalytic degradation of the dye at low concentrations obeyed first order kinetics. The linear plot of $\log C_0/C$ versus irradiation time (*t*) on ZnO/C is shown in Fig. 10. The effect of solute concentration on the rate of photocatalytic degradation can be explained on the basis of Langmuir-Hinshelwood expression²⁹ as given below :

$$r = \frac{k_1 k_2 C_0}{1 + k_1 C_0}$$

where k_1 , k_2 and C_0 are adsorption constant, specific rate constant and initial concentration of the dye respectively. The applicability of equation was confirmed by the linear plot obtained by reciprocal of initial rate $1/r$ against reciprocal of initial concentration of the dye $1/C_0$ on ZnO/C (Fig. 11). The values of k_1 and k_2 were found to be $0.017 \mu\text{M}^{-1}$ and $1.54 \mu\text{M}/\text{min}$ respectively. The product

Fig. 11. Plot of $1/r$ versus $1/C_0$ for acid yellow 110. Catalyst = ZnO/C (0.5 g/L); pH = 6.2; Temp. = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 420 nm.

of k_1 and k_2 was found to be tallied with the apparent rate constant value obtained at low initial dye concentrations. Additional support for this conclusion arises from the calculation of $t_{0.5}$ which is the time taken for completion of half of the reaction. Half-life ($t_{0.5}$) of the degradation reaction is evaluated using the following equation,

$$t_{0.5} = \frac{0.5C_0}{k_2} + \frac{0.693}{k_1 k_2}$$

A plot of $t_{0.5}$ versus $0.5C_0$ yielded straight line (Fig. 12), whose slope is $1/k_2$ and slope/intercept is $k_1/0.693$. The photocatalytic degradation of the dye AY 110 was found to obey first order kinetics at low dye concentration. A plot of $\log C_0/C$ vs irradiation time t , as shown in Fig. 10 was found to be linear, confirming first order kinetics adherence.

Fig. 12. Plot of $t_{0.5}$ versus $0.5 C_0$ for acid yellow 110. Catalyst = ZnO/C (0.5 g/L); pH = 6.2; Temp. = 30.0 ± 0.1 °C; incident wavelength = 254 nm; absorbance measured at 420 nm.

Mechanism of photocatalytic degradation :

The photocatalytic process is initiated by the illumination of a ZnO/C semiconductor nanocatalyst with radiation of energy higher than the band gap energy of the semiconductor. This irradiation generates electrons (e^-) and holes (h^+) in the conduction band and valence band as given by the following equation [eq. (1)].

The electron-hole pair formed may recombine in the bulk

lattice or migrate to the surface where they can react with the adsorbates³⁰. The principle hole traps are commonly believed to adsorb hydroxide ions or water molecules. Hole trapping reactions are commonly proceeds with the formation of hydroxyl radicals (OH^\bullet) as given by the following equations [eqs. (2) and (3)].

The photo excited electrons (e^-) are trapped by the dissolved oxygen present in the reaction solution in the formation of superoxide ion radicals ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$) as represented in eq. (4).

The superoxide anion radical may be further reduced to hydrogen peroxide and cleaves to OH^\bullet radical and shown in following equations [eqs. (5), (6) and (7)].

The possible reaction scheme for the photocatalytic degradation of AB 113 by ZnO/C nano composite can be proposed to be,

Electrical energy efficiency :

The study of light intensity on the photo conversion efficiency has attracted great attention of many researches, across the globe. The determination of electrical energy by order of magnitude E_{E0} has turned out to be the essential merit of the photocatalytic system, as per the IUPAC expectations. E_{E0} is termed as the light energy in kWh required for scavenging the concentration of pollutant by one order of magnitude i.e. 95%, in 1 m^3 of contaminated water. The required UV dose and as well the value of E_{E0} was arrived from a plot of energy dose (kWh m^{-3}) versus inverse of the slope of a plot of $\log (C_0/C)^{31}$, where C_0 and C are the initial and final AY 110 concentrations at any desired time interval, chosen for the study. The time required for the 95% decolorization of a litre of solution containing $60 \mu\text{M}$ of AY 110 was 90 min, at a pH of 6.2 with a catalyst concentration of 0.5 g L^{-1} . The E_{E0} value has been found to be 9 kWh m^{-3} . However, the time required for the same 95% decolorization of a litre

of solution containing 60 μM of AY 110 was found to be 160 min, at a pH of 8 with the same catalyst concentration of 0.5 g/L. The E_{E0} value has been found to be 16 kWh m^{-3} .

Photocatalytic degradation of textile effluent :

The textile effluent collected from the industry was treated with ZnO/C nano composite and the reduction in the COD was observed as shown in the Fig. 13. The reduction in the COD confirms the destruction of organic molecules in the effluents along with color removal.

Fig. 13. COD of the effluent at different time intervals.

Experimental

Materials :

The dye, acid yellow 110 (AY 110) commercially known as acid yellow 5GN was obtained from local dye suppliers and the dye was used without further purification. The structure of the dye is shown in Fig. 1. The dye shows an absorption maximum at 420 nm. The dye solutions of the desired concentrations were prepared using double distilled water. The other chemicals like $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, dextrose and ZnO were of AR grade obtained from Merck. The pH of the solutions was adjusted between 5.0 and 8.0 using dilute solutions of HCl or NaOH.

Synthesis of ZnO/carbon nano composite :

The ZnO/C nano composite was synthesized by self-propagating solution combustion method²¹. In this 10 g of zinc nitrate was dissolved in 20 mL of double distilled water and 3.6 g of dextrose was dissolved in 20 mL of

double distilled water in separate beakers. Dextrose solution was heated on a hot plate for 5 min, when the solution begins to boil the zinc nitrate solution was added in a dropwise with constant stirring. The solution dehydrates and forms gel like mass. Then the beaker was heated in a preheated muffle furnace at 400 °C. The solution boils, ignites with a flame and the entire reaction was completed within 7 min. The powder obtained was highly amorphous and the presence of ZnO and carbon was confirmed by the EDAX pattern of the composite. The ZnO/C composite catalyst samples with different amount of carbon loading were prepared by varying the amount of dextrose.

Photocatalytic reaction procedure :

The experimental studies were carried out in a batch reactor consisting of a rectangular glass vessel made of borosilicate glass. The reactor containing a dye solution and the catalyst was kept over magnetic stirrer. Photo irradiation was carried out using a low pressure mercury vapour lamp (6 W, 18 cm long) emitting UV radiation at a peak wavelength of 254 nm. The reactor set up was covered with a wooden box which was covered by aluminium foil to prevent exposure to UV light. The experiments were conducted by taking a 250 mL of dye solution of the required concentration with a known weight of photocatalyst. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained constant throughout the reaction time. Stirring of the solution was carried out in the dark for 30 min, to establish adsorption-desorption equilibrium. Further the mixture was irradiated with UV light and a sample of 3 mL was withdrawn at regular intervals and centrifuged. The concentration of the dye solution was measured spectrophotometrically and returned to the reactor. The same photocatalytic experimental setup was used for the treatment of effluent consisting of dye acid yellow 110. The effluent was used without any pretreatment except that the effluent was diluted in order to facilitate the light penetration. The photodegradation reaction was followed by the estimation of chemical oxygen demand.

Characterization techniques :

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained using Rigaku X-ray diffractometer, Japan. The crystalline phase of ZnO was identified by comparing with JCPDS card no. 36-1451. The SEM photographs of ZnO/C were obtained by using a high resolution scanning electron mi-

croscope (Carlzeiss, Supra 55, Germany). The BET surface area measurements were carried out using Micromeritics, ASAP 2020 V3.01 G and UV studies were carried out using SL-210 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer.

Conclusions

The nanoZnO/C composite was found to be effective catalyst for the degradation of acid yellow 110 when compared with commercial ZnO and pristine nanoZnO. The optimum carbon loading on nanoZnO was observed as 10%. The removal of dye was maximum at pH 6.2. The degradation rate increased with increase in initial concentration of the dye and reached a limited value. The optimum catalyst loading was found to be 0.5 g L⁻¹. The dye degradation obeyed first order kinetics and could be explained on the basis of Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism. The required time for 95% decolorization of the one liter of solution containing 60 µM of dye at pH 6.2 was 90 min, the E_{E0} value has been determined as 9 kWh m⁻³. The textile effluents were treated successfully. The reduction in COD values confirmed the destruction of the organics present in the effluents.

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